

CHILDREN'S CHARACTER

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ABSTRACT: There are too many children here who are affected by family situations. The family ensures that the child becomes self-confident and responsible. Children have many opportunities to speak. A child's pursuit of life is very interesting. There are shows on TV that are harmful to children.

KEYWORDS: Healthy personality development, child development period, highly distressing, trauma, social and emotional exchanges, impact thought process, moral issues, “normal” children.

Many theorists agree that social contact early in a child's life is crucial for healthy personality development. This is the most significant relationship of the child development period as it is from this that the child derives its confidence and in the world. A break from this relationship is experienced as highly distressing and lead a considerable trauma. Through frequent social and emotional exchanges with parents the infant not only defines itself, but also acquires a particular style and orientation which some researchers believe is carried over into later life. Thus, the relationship between an infant and its care giver and its development is one that has generated much interest to developmental psychologists. It is true that, from the minute you are born the family effect starts to impact your thought process. A child is like a sponge that absorbs ideas and beliefs. Beliefs are taught to a child in minor ways such as just listening to the parents and their ideas from everything containing politics, social problems, moral issues and even opinions about how others behave. It is within the family unit that a person learns their moral values. It is from their parents that a child is taught right and wrong. “Normal” children, that is, those who

have not had a particularly rich environment usually begin talking after the first year of their life. By eighteen months they have a vocabulary of about half a dozen words and at two years a vocabulary of more than a hundred words. The traditional view has been that during the first year of life, babies are not mature enough to learn languages. Talking, however, is only the outer manifestation of the development of the language long before he first utters a meaningful word a baby can be observed responding to the language of the others. Children's character remains a controversial topic. For example, a child will always tire of a toy when he no longer has any difficulty using it. He is like the boy with a bicycle; as long as he finds it difficult to avoid trees and to turn corners, so long will he spend all his spare time on it. But once he has thoroughly mastered it, he will only use it as a means of getting about, and not for its own sake. It is an unhealthy child who has no creative interest. Keep a child busy and he will be happy, and conversely, a happy child will always be busy. Many experiments have suggested that a child who has watched a violent video sequence is more likely to engage in aggressive acts than one who has not. According to one study, a preference for violent TV shows is a more accurate indicator of aggression than socio-economic background, family relationship, IQ, or any other single factor. Though it is difficult to say which comes first, an aggressive personality or a preference for violent shows, the relationship is certainly valid. A steady diet of TV violence can also make children numb to reality. One eleven years old was quoted as saying that he had seen so many assaults and murders on the screen that if he saw someone really get killed, it would not bother him. A recent opinion poll discovered that many people were very concerned about the amount of violence depicted in movies, television shows, and popular music. This poll also discovered, however, that most people thought that individuals should take responsibility to correct the problems. The vast majority favored such solutions as tighter parental supervision, warning labels on records, and voluntary self-restraints by entertainment companies. Only 27 per cent favored government censorship. At the same time, there was growing concern about the impact of television on children.

Research has shown that by the time our children reach age 18, they have spent more time watching television than in school. The problem was that our television system was attuned the market place . Children are treated as a market to be sold to advertisers at so much money per thousand eyeballs.

References:

1. Usmonova, D. (2022). TO STUDY THE IMPORTANCE OF TRANSPOSITION OF WORD CATEGORIES IN ENGLISH. *O'ZBEKISTONDA FANLARARO INNOVATSIYALAR VA ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR JURNALI*, 1(10), 128-131.
2. Ortiqov, R. (2022, June). STRUCTURAL AND SEMANTICAL FEATURES AND DIFFERENCES OF ORAL AND WRITTEN SPEECH. In *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCES ON LEARNING AND TEACHING* (Vol. 1, No. 9, pp. 438-442).
3. Abdumalik o'g'li, O. R. (2021). THE BRIEF INVESTIGATION OF CONTEMPORARY SPEECH STYLES OF THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 9(12), 1280-1283.
4. BO, I. T. N. O. R., & TAVSIYALAR, Y. A. M. R. Ortiqov–Farg ‘ona davlat universiteti o ‘qituvchisi. *FARG ‘ONA DAVLAT UNIVERSITETI*, 128.
5. Abdumalik o'g'li, O. R. Cultural Comparison of Uzbek and English Language Speech Styles.
6. Yakubova, D. (2022). TEACHING GRAMMAR FOR EFL STUDENTS AND ITS APPROACHES. *Involta Scientific Journal*, 1(7), 265-268.
7. Dilnozakhon, Y. (2022). TEACHING PRAGMATICS BY EXPRESSING AND GIVING COMPLIMENTS. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 3(6), 575-578.
8. Mirzayeva, D. (2021). PROVERBS AND SAYINGS AS A PRODUCT OF THE NATION'S COGNITIVE THINKING. In *Multidiscipline*

- Proceedings of Digital Fashion Conference* (Vol. 1, No. 2). Ismoilova, S., & Xalilova, G. (2022). RESEARCH ON THE ISSUE OF QUESTIONS IN LINGUISTICS. *Development and innovations in science*, 1(1), 17-19.
9. Soxibovna, M. G. (2022, August). THE ROLE OF LINGUISTICS IN THE STUDY OF NATIONAL AND CULTURAL FEATURES OF SPEECH UNITS. In INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE: PROBLEMS AND SCIENTIFIC SOLUTIONS. (Vol. 1, No. 3, pp. 48-52).
10. Rafailovna, T. G. (2020). Code-switching in teaching a foreign language. *Проблемы современной науки и образования*, (3 (148)), 69-71.
11. Muzaffarovna, A. N., & Qizi, A. S. T. (2020). Characteristic features of word formation of a newspaper article in English and Uzbek languages. *Проблемы современной науки и образования*, (2 (147)), 41-43.
12. Hoshimova, N. A. (2020). Ingliz va o'zbek tillarining funktsional uslublari. *Молодой ученый*, (19), 584-585.
13. Abbasova, N. K. (2018). Using Effective Techniques Developing Learners' Critical Thinking in Teaching English Proverbs and Sayings. *Eastern European Scientific Journal*, (6).
14. Abbasova, N. (2019). Using effective techniques for developing critical thinking of the learners while teaching english proverbs and sayings. *Scientific journal of the Fergana State University*, 2(3), 107-110.

Internet resources:

1. <https://www.verywellfamily.com>
2. <https://www.childwelfare.gov>